

INFORMATION SYSTEMS TECHNOLOGY PLAN FOR SABON DEPOT

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ABSTRACT

In a world where technology is enhancing some businesses, we are growing with the help of IT Infrastructure. Having IT infrastructure in a business enhances the company's productivity, decision-making, and overall growth.

Unfortunately, our team decided to apply three systems, including the Point of Sale (POS) system, to help the company streamline its operations and processing and help in decision-making. Inventory Management System to track the products effectively to avoid problems. The activity-based costing (ABC) system will assist the company in identifying business processes to reduce unnecessary complications. These three systems should be implemented to enhance the productivity of the company.

Hence, employing these systems and also other computer related keys can be significant in eliminating errors and to strengthen business productivity, decision making, and performance.

Keywords: Point of Sale (POS) System, Business process, Inventory Management System, Activity-based Costing (ABC) System, information system

INTRODUCTION

1.1 BACKGROUND OF THE COMPANY

Sabon Depot is a manufacturing business that produces cleaning products for households and commercial use. The Sabon Depot was established in 2018 by a group of fifteen individuals who shared

common interests in creating a business that offers a high-quality yet affordable product for consumers. The company aims to meet the growing demand for effective and budget-friendly personal or household items while maintaining product quality and customer satisfaction. The founders brought together their expertise in building a business that could stand out in the competitive market of hygiene and cleaning products. Before the Sabon Depot was established in Mindanao, the enterprise operated under Clean Up Solution Enterprise Incorporated.

Furthermore, the business operated in Manila, but then the Sabon Depot was expanded in Mindanao. The Panabo Branch was established on July 24, 2019, by Jovito Glodo, and it is located at Service Road, Panabo City, Davao del Norte. The business expansion marked a significant milestone, meeting new markets and communities across the southern area of the Philippines. Through franchise, the Sabon Depot established forty-six branches across Mindanao, which allows the business to serve a wide range of customers. This growth reflects the company's strong foundation, strategic vision, and commitment to making quality products accessible to every Filipino consumer.

Additionally, Sabon Depot uses its Facebook page to promote a product, keeping the customers informed about its products and special offers. The company sells chemicals in drums, gallons, and

receptacles, which will be delivered to franchises and customers. This demonstrates the strong production efficiency. Sabon Depot produces a minimum of 60 drums of chemical cleaning products daily. After production, the drums can either be sold, added to the inventory, or transferred to containers, gallons, and bottles.

The business aims to produce at least a minimum of 60 drums per day to meet the high demand and especially to maintain the efficient production of its products for its customers. By accomplishing the target this ensures the availability of products, supports market demands, and customer satisfaction.

1.2 CURRENT ROUTINES AND BUSINESS PROCESS

1.2.1 Current Routines

The business operates from 8:00 am to 5:00 pm on Mondays to Sundays. Each day, there is a set of strict procedures aimed at maintaining the company's standards of having clean, safe, and high-quality products. In production, they will prepare and sanitize the drum that was used in manufacturing. The critical aspect of this is the use of water for production. In producing soap products, they did not use normal water for production; instead, the water that is used is deionized so that they can provide good quality in producing their product.

Before proceeding with full-scale production, the company conducts strict testing using specialized testers. These tools are used to measure and verify the soap formulation, ensuring the correct ratios of ingredients are used, enabling the business to provide high-quality products. If those are entered, the standard that they follow, they will proceed in production.

Table 1. Event Table of Sabon Depot

Start Time	End Time	Description	Duration
7:45 AM	8:00 AM	Time in	15 minutes
8:00 AM	11:30 AM	Working hours	3 hours and 30 minutes
11:30 AM	1:00 PM	Lunch Break	1 hour and 30 minutes
1:00 PM	4:30 PM	Working hours in Production	3 hours and 30 minutes

Table 1 shows daily events that were performed by the employees of Sabon Depot.

1.2.2 Business Process

The Sabon Depot manufactures soap products for its customers. The production process begins with forecasting, which assists the business in determining the demand and plans accordingly. This allows them to identify the necessary raw materials and prepare them in the required quantities. Once the materials are ready, the process moves to the production area, where the soap products are manufactured. After production, the items are transferred to the packaging department.

In addition, after the packaging, the products are sent to the distribution stage, wherein the dispatcher is responsible for allocating the goods to Store A, Store B, Store C, and Store D. Once the deliveries are done, the dispatcher returns with the delivery receipts. The receipts are processed by the accounting department, which handles the financial recording and reconciliation. This cycle is repeated daily as part of the company's regular operations.

1.3 Problems Found

- Lack of proper product costing.** One of the problems identified in the Sabon depot is the lack of proper product costing, which makes it difficult to determine the actual costs of the products or services. Without an activity-based costing system, the business could encounter inaccurate pricing due to failure to account for the specific activities and resources used to produce the products.
- Lack of effective and efficient Inventory Management System.** Aside from proper product costing. The researchers identified the lack of an effective inventory management system at Sabon Depot, making it difficult to monitor the stocks of raw materials and finished goods. This often leads to problems such as overstocking and stockouts. The challenge of managing and controlling the stocks of goods can lead to financial losses, operational inefficiencies, and customer dissatisfaction.

1.4 Goals and Objectives

1.4.1 General Objectives

The Researchers aim to propose an IT infrastructure that includes implementing a Point of Sale (POS) System to enhance the sales process, improve inventory management, and generate accurate sales reports that will assist in the improvement of overall business operations. Inventory Management System helps in supporting the tracking, controlling, and optimizing of stock levels. The Activity Costing System provides more accurate costs than the traditional methods.

1.4.2 Specific Objectives

- Automate the sales transactions process and minimize human error.
- To monitor and manage inventory in real-time.
- To generate accurate and timely sales reports for better business decision-making.
- To improve customer service by reducing transaction time at the counter.

1.5 Organizational Structure

Figure 1: Organizational Structure of Sabon Depot

The Sabon Depot is a manufacturing business, but before it became one, it was initially founded in Manila by a company called Clean Up Solutio Enterprise Incorporated. This enterprise initially focused on providing cleaning products and services.

1.6 Stakeholders

Figure 2: Stakeholders of Sabon Depot

Owner, employees, customers, suppliers, communities, and government are considered stakeholders of Sabon Depot, as shown in Figure 2.

PROPOSED INFORMATION SYSTEM

The researchers proposed a Point of Sale (POS) System, an Inventory Management System, and an Activity-based Costing System to attain growth in obtaining unbiased data, production, and business operations.

2.1 Name of IS

A point of Sale (POS) System streamlines the operations of a company, which helps to accommodate many customers for fast and efficient service. A Point of Sale (POS) System, besides processing purchases, provides insights into sales trends, employee productivity inventory levels, customer preferences, and more [15].

Inventory Management System a combination of technology, processes and procedures used to track, manage, and optimize a company's inventory. Inventory Management System allows employee or manager to track, record, and overview product stocks that are coming in and out from the company inventory to ensure there is no unexpected low on stock or overstock occur [13].

Activity-based Costing (ABC) System is a way to determine how much a product or service really costs by looking at the actual activities and resources used to produce it. An activity-based costing system helps businesses like the Sabon Depot. If the Sabon depot uses ABC, it can identify that mixing chemicals and labeling bottles consume more resources than packaging. In short, the ABC helps to calculate more accurate product costs, understand what processes consume the most resources, improve pricing decisions and profitability analysis, and reduce unnecessary expenses [14].

2.1.1 Related Literature

Sabon Depot is a small-scale business that specializes in the production of cleaning products. Because of having limited resources, the company struggles to monitor the real-time cost of goods sold, especially the usage of raw materials and labor per item. While there are big, comprehensive ERP systems available, they are often costly and challenging to implement. This study suggests a simpler approach: developing and implementing a basic point of sale (POS), inventory tracking, and a costing module that will help the business manage its operational efficiency without going over the budget. The company can improve how it makes decisions step-by-step by using these systems individually. A point of sale (POS) system is a tool used to record sales transactions. It is the place where the customer pays for the products or services they purchase. With the help of POS, businesses can replace manual writing or calculators and improve the accuracy and speed of their sales process. Additionally, the POS can be used personally or for online processes. The feasibility of online POS Systems is specifically designed for small and medium enterprises in Bangladesh. Furthermore, Modern POS systems also offer features like inventory tracking, reporting, and integration with other business tools [1].

Nowadays, point-of-sale (POS) systems are popular in developing countries because they provide fast and convenient ways for businesses to make transactions. These systems contain vital tasks such as online transactions, e-commerce facilities, security, taxes, various management reports, and many more [3]. Therefore, with a large volume of customers in supermarkets and the growing competitive business

environment in developing countries, ensuring software quality becomes very important for them. A recent study points out that a POS system is not only for handling sales; it can also work well with other business tools, making it easier to connect sales, inventory, and product cost. An inventory management system (IMS) is important since it helps the business to track both materials used to make products and finished products. For manufacturing businesses like the Sabon Depot, it is helpful to know how many chemicals, bottles, and labels are still available in stock. When the customers buy or order products, the system should automatically update the numbers of stock [4]. According to Joshi (2024), the separation of POS and inventory management systems (IMS) helps small businesses manage their stocks without needing an extensive, expensive system. They also add that this kind of setup helps the owner see which materials are moving fast and which ones are rarely used [5].

To better understand how this system developed and evolved, it is helpful to look at the history of product costing. Traditional costing and activity-based costing are methods that have developed over time as a part of their evolution. The traditional costing system is one of the oldest methods and was commonly used in the past when factories relied on manual labor. This method adds all the indirect costs and then spreads them out using one cost driver. A "cost driver," such as labor hours or machine hours. By this traditional costing, it leads to unfair or inaccurate costing. On the other hand, activity-based costing (ABC) is also a factor. This method is more detailed and accurate. How does it work? Instead of looking at the indirect costs or the hours worked, it looks at all processes involved in making products, like the materials, packaging, inspection, etc. Then, it assigns costs based on how much each product uses those processes. Kenton (2024) also highlights that the ABC is much more compatible with modern technology and complex businesses today [6].

Furthermore, in businesses like coffee shops, POS paved the way for difficulty in operating the business. POS systems allow these businesses to enhance transaction handling, stock management, client relations, and general functioning [7]. Other than that, inventory is also essential for the improvement of the business; efficient inventory

management is essential for companies to maintain seamless operations, reduce expenses, and provide high-quality services in today's fast-changing environment [8]. In the Philippines, the government is actively seeking and utilizing Information technology products and applications [9].

Moreover, information technology is not only used by the government and business establishments, but banana growers are also using information technology in operating their businesses. Banana growers in Kapalong, Davao del Norte, used information technology to handle the business and enhance their productivity [10]. Having effective inventory management is crucial because it involves determining the current and future inventory needs. This helps in preventing excess stock while also ensuring that there will be no shortage that can cause delays in production [11]. To avoid too much or not enough stock is to use the Sales and Inventory Management System, which approaches in line with daily sales data from the Point of Sales system directly on the store's current inventory levels [12].

In conclusion, for a small-scale manufacturing business like the Sabon Depot that is facing resource limitations, which affects the business operations, the implementation of this basic integrated system, which includes POS, Inventory Management System, and the Costing System, presents a viable and budget-friendly solution. Having this step-by-step approach allows the business to improve its operational efficiency by automating sales processes, providing real time inventory visibility, and also enabling more accurate product costing. By moving away from those manual methods and embracing a simplified digital system, the Sabon Depot can mitigate the common issues that are facing, which leads to better decision-making and enhanced profitability.

2.1.2 Functionality

Point of Sale (POS) System

- This makes the sales process run smoothly by automating the transactions
- This records real-time sales and also generates receipts
- This tracks the customer's purchase history

- This integrates with inventory for its stock updates
- This provides the sales reports and analytics for business perception

Inventory Management System

- This monitors the stock amount in real time
- This can prevent overstocking and stockouts
- This automates the reordering process
- This generates detailed inventory reports for auditing

Activity Costing System

- This allocates costs to specific business activities
- This helps to identify high-cost and low-efficiency operations
- This provides accurate cost data for budgeting and pricing
- This improves financial planning
- This can support strategic decision-making by analyzing the cost trait

2.1.3 System Architecture

Figure 3: System Architecture of Sabon Depot

2.1.4 Economic Feasibility

Table 2. Economic Feasibility of Sabon Depot

Cost Description	Cost
Operational Cost	Php 55,000.00
Development Cost	Php 27,599.00
Maintenance Cost	Php10,000.00
Total Cost	Php 92,599.00

Table 2. Unveil the overall costs of the business if the proposed system is applied.

PROPOSED IT INFRASTRUCTURE

The observations of the researchers lead them to focus on the improvement and productivity of the business and the employees. In which the problem has an impact on the enhancement of the business operations, the researchers considered the following components needed for the business improvement.

3.1 Proposed Computer Hardware

The hardware infrastructure is combined with the rapidly evolving technologies to ensure business operations run efficiently. This enables the company to operate strongly with decent hardware.

Table 3. Proposed Computer Hardware of Sabon Depot

Computer Hardware	Specification	Unit Cost	Quantity	Total Cost
Desktop Computer	Core i5, 8GB RAM, 1TB SSD, Windows 11	Php 25,000	2	Php 50,000
Barcode Scanner	USB Laser Barcode Scanner	Php 3,000	2	Php 6,000
Receipt Printer	Thermal Printer	Php 5,000	2	Php 10,000
Router and Switch	Gigabit Router with 16-port switch	Php 5,500	1	Php 5,500
Total Cost of Computer Hardware				Php 71,500

Table 3. Unveil the overall computer hardware cost of Sabon Depot if the proposed plan is applied.

3.2 Proposed Operating System

The Operating System is essential as it acts as the backbone of a computer, coordinating between the hardware and software to ensure everything functions efficiently.

Table 4. Proposed Operating System of Sabon Depot

OS Platform	Specification	Unit Cost	Quantity	Total Cost
Windows 11	64-bit, licensed	Php 14,999	1	Php 14,999
Total Cost of Operating System				Php 14,999

Table 4. Unveil the overall operating system cost of Sabon Depot if the proposed plan is applied.

3.3 Proposed Data Management

This assists businesses in organizing, storing, and analyzing their business data, which also supports decisions and maintains accurate records.

Table 5. Proposed Data Management of Sabon Depot

Data Management Tool	Specification	Unit Cost	Quantity	Total Cost
Microsoft 365 Suite	Excel, Access, and OneDrive for reports and backup	Php 670	1	Php 670
Total Cost of Data Management				Php 670

Table 5. Unveil the overall operating system cost of the Sabon depot if the proposed plan is applied.

3.4 Proposed Internet Platform

The essence of having an Internet Platform enables online transactions in the business. Helps in expanding business reach and accessibility.

Table 6. Proposed Internet Platform of Sabon Depot

Internet Platform	Specification	Unit Cost	Quantity	Total Cost
E-Commerce	Online Platform for customer transactions, payments, and order tracking	Free	1	Free

Table 6. Unveil the overall internet platform cost of Sabon Depot if the proposed plan will be applied.

3.5 Proposed Network and Telecommunication

Having a Network and Telecommunications helps connect devices within or across the branches, ensuring smooth communication and system access.

Table 7. Proposed Network and Telecommunication of Sabon Depot

Network	Specification	Unit Cost	Quantity	Total Cost
LAN	The LAN is essential in connecting computers and devices within the office or store. It enables fast and secure sharing of data.	Php 5,000	1	Php 10,000

Table 7. Unveil the overall network and telecommunication cost of Sabon Depot if the proposed plan is applied.

3.6 Proposed IT Manpower

Having skilled personnel helps the business maintain its systems, resolve issues, and ensure its continuous operations.

Table 8. Proposed IT Manpower of Sabon Depot

IT Manpower	Job Description	Proposed Salary
IT Support Technician	Provide technical support and troubleshooting for hardware and software issues.	Php 17,000/mo [16]

Table 8. Unveil the overall cost of the IT manpower of Sabon Depot if the proposed plan is applied.

3.7 Prototype

Figure 4: Prototype for Sabon Depot

Dashboard

This prototype suits our chosen business, which is the Sabon Depot Manufacturing Company. It helps improve the monitoring and sales performance. The dashboard provides an organized view of total earnings, total orders, and customer ratings.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

4.1 Conclusion

Based on the outcome, the study shows that Sabon Depot is lacking in the Point-of-Sale System and needs to improve its inventory to enable the business to provide effective decision-making for the company. Aside from that the improvement of its costing system. The ideas that were proposed are the best way to improve the business operations and

modify the traditional ways of operating the business.

4.2 Recommendation

Based on the findings of this study, several recommendations are given to help improve the daily operation of the company while keeping the system affordable and practical for small-scale manufacturing businesses like Sabon Depot.

- Train staff on system use
- Plan for the future system integration
- Maintain accurate pricing
- Monitor stock levels regularly
- Update raw materials prices
- Do regular system checks
- Back-up and data storage
- Check system performance
- Keep inventory and cost data updated
- Implement user access controls
- Provide customer support integration

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EDUCATION

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DAVAO DEL NORTE STATE COLLEGE
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CARMEN NATIONAL HIGH SCHOOL
 • Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMSS)

SKILLS

- Project Management
- Public Relations
- Teamwork
- Time Management
- Leadership
- Effective Communication
- Critical Thinking

LANGUAGES

- English
- Filipino
- Cebuano

PROFILE

I am a hardworking student who is dedicated, willing to learn, and able to adapt to different tasks and challenges. I do my best in every job, listen well, and work nicely with others. I stay focused even when things are hard, and I always try to learn and grow from every experience.

WORK EXPERIENCE

- Information System Student** 2024- PRESENT
 - Currently studying Information System
 - Participates in school project and activities related to IT
- Secretary - School Club** 2023-2024
 - Helped plan and organize school activities and events
 - Kept important documents and organized schedules
 - Showed responsibility and good time management
- HUMSS Student - Community Engagement** 2023-2024
 - Participated in community outreach and service-learning activities aimed at social awareness and development
 - Conducted interviews, surveys, and documentation as part of community profiling
 - Facilitated small group discussions during immersion and reflection sessions
 - Promoted civic responsibility through collaborative projects with local barangay officials

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EDUCATION

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2022-2023
F. BUSTAMANTE NATIONAL HIGH SCHOOL

- TVL - Electrical Installation and maintenance
- GPA 94%

SKILLS

- Tech Adaptability
- Basic Electrical Installation
- Computer Literacy
- Teamwork
- Time Management
- Leadership
- Effective Communication
- Critical Thinking

LANGUAGES

- English
- Tagalog
- Cebuano

PROFILE

I am a hardworking and motivated student with a deep interest in learning new skills and gaining practical knowledge. I enjoy working with others, solving problem, and always do my best in everything I do

WORK EXPERIENCE

- Information system student** 2024-PRESENT
 - Currently studying Information System
 - Continuously improving skills in technology, business and computer system
 - Participates in school projects and activities related to IT
- Volunteer - Campus clean-up and Electrical Assistance** 2023-2024
 - Promoted safety and teamwork among classmates, students, staff and teachers during activities
 - Assisted teachers and students demonstrating basic electrical work
 - Helped clean and maintain the school campus, and assisted teachers and student during school event
- On-The-Job Training (OJT)** 2022-2023
 - Assisted in installing electrical circuits, switches and wires
 - Helped maintain tools and ensure a safe work area
 - Observed and learned from licensed electrician

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PANABO CITY SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL
 • Accountancy Business and Management Strand

SKILLS

- Project Management
- Public Relations
- Teamwork
- Time Management
- Leadership
- Effective Communication
- Critical Thinking

LANGUAGES

- English
- Filipino
- Cebuano

PROFILE

Highly motivated, adaptable, and hardworking individual with a strong commitment in prioritizing tasks and achieving objectives. Possesses excellent interpersonal and communication skills, enabling effective collaboration and positive social interactions. Eager to apply a dedicated work ethic and a proactive approach to contribute to the company's goals in a challenging role.

WORK EXPERIENCE

- Information System Student** 2024-Present
 - Currently studying Information Systems
 - Continuously enhancing skills and knowledge in technology, business and computer system
- On the Job Training (OJT)** 2023-2024
 - Assisted in preparing, and editing financial reports
 - Assisted in documents
- Volunteer in Tree planting** 2022-2023
 - Helped in planting trees and assisted others students and teachers during the activity.

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EDUCATION

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FRANCISCO ADLON LEARNING INSTITUTE INC.
 • TVL - Computer systems servicing

SKILLS

- Project Management
- Teamwork
- Time Management
- Effective Communication
- Critical Thinking
- Computer skills (Hardware and Software)
- Tech Adaptability

LANGUAGES

- ENGLISH
- TAGALOG
- CEBUANO

PROFILE

I am a hardworking student, deeply interested in learning new skills and knowledge from others and applying it to myself. I enjoy working alone and with a team, and always giving my best.

WORK EXPERIENCE

- Information System Student** 2024- PRESENT
 - Currently pursuing a degree in Information Systems
 - Computer Troubleshooting (Hardware and Software)
 - Actively enhancing skills in Information Systems, including hardware and software support
- Panabo City Hall Event Staff (BINULUG)** 2023-2024
 - Event Photographer
 - Event Staff
- On-The-Job Training (OJT)** 2023-2024
 - Officer/Clerk
 - Head and staff assistant
 - Computer troubleshooting
 - Event staff
 - Event photographer
 - Distributed flyers to city guests
 - Observing how professionals work under pressure